

University Marine Energy Research Community

2023 Conference

4-6 October | Durham, NH, USA

Spatio-Temporal Variability of Tidal Velocities in Kootznahoo Inlet: Bathymetry and Velocity Characterization

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Abstract

As part of a project with the U.S. Department of Energy (DoE) Advanced Research Projects Agency-Energy (ARPA-E), Littoral Power Systems, Inc. (LPS) will design, fabricate, and test a fully integrated subscale hydrokinetic current energy conversion device in the Kootznahoo Inlet in Angoon, Alaska. To determine an optimal location for the device, a survey of the tidal flows in the Inlet was performed to measure the spatial and temporal variability of ebb and flood currents. Quasi-synoptic measurements of current speed and direction were recorded throughout the transect cycles. A DYNLET hydrodynamic model was also developed for the Inlet to obtain spatial and temporal velocity variations. The model was calibrated and validated using the measured transect velocity data and then used to predict velocity estimates throughout the inlet and over the tidal cycle. Comparative results show that the strongest flows were found consistently on the peak flood and ebb tide, close to the southeast side of the inlet (close to the Village Rock) in relatively shallow water depth.

Keywords: Kootznahoo Inlet; ADCP; Angoon; tidal current velocity; spatio-temporal variability; hydrodynamic modeling; hydrokinetic marine energy.

1. Introduction

Alaskan waters contain about 94% of the theoretical US tidal energy potential [1]. Parts of the state see some of the highest electricity rates in the nation. Hence, many early US efforts to develop tidal energy projects have occurred in Alaska. It is well understood that the power density in a moving water slab is proportional to the cube of its velocity [2]. Accordingly, all things being equal, the best sites for current energy conversion are the ones with the highest velocities. However, selecting a location for device deployment must consider additional considerations, including distance to power distribution assets, environmental considerations such as potential impacts on fish or marine mammals, and competing water resource uses such as navigation and fishing [3]. There have been numerous studies of the hydrokinetic energy resource in Alaska, including studies of tidal energy at the statewide level [1], the resource in Cook Inlet [4], the resource in False Pass [5], as well as riverine energy resources [6, 7]. Accordingly, LPS is applying a Control Co-Design (CCD) engineering process [8] involving a multi-disciplinary approach to characterize and numerically optimize this framework. This paper focuses on the characterization part of the CCD process involving the spatial and temporal distribution of velocity and bathymetry in the Kootznahoo Inlet.

To characterize the velocity distribution, a field campaign was designed and executed. An aerial view of the Gulf of Alaska encompassing the town of Angoon is shown in Fig. 1(a). In 2021, LPS was granted a preliminary permit

for the Kootznahoo Inlet Tidal Energy Project (KITEP) by the US Federal Energy Regulatory Commission (FERC); the project boundary is shown in Fig. 1(b). A field campaign was designed and executed to characterize the velocity distribution. The team measured bathymetry throughout Kootznahoo Inlet and captured velocity and water level data throughout various tidal cycles on selected transects. A DYNLET hydrodynamic model was also developed for the Inlet to estimate the spatial and temporal velocity distribution. The model was calibrated and validated using velocity measurements to estimate velocity throughout the Inlet and over the tidal cycle.

Fig. 1. (a) Aerial view of Kootznahoo Inlet (Angoon, Alaska); (b) Preliminary permit project boundary (FERC Project No. P15110-000).

2. Instrumentation and Survey Techniques

Bathymetric surveys and current velocity measurements in Kootznahoo Inlet were conducted in late September 2022. The fieldwork had the following objectives: (i) establish survey control using differential GPS, (ii) survey bathymetry along pre-planned transects using a real-time kinematic (RTK) GPS and integrated depth sounder, (iii) measure current velocities at separate phases of the tidal cycle using a downward-looking ADCP, (iv) measure water surface elevations using submerged pressure transducers, and (v) obtain video imagery of the Inlet seabed.

2.1. Experimental setup

A two-member field team from Michael Baker International (MBI) mounted the RTK GPS, an integrated single-beam depth sounder, and an ADCP on a 20-foot Hewes craft boat [9]. The vessel-mounted equipment configuration and corresponding offsets are shown in Fig. 2(a). The data acquisition system consisted of a laptop running Teledyne WinRiverII SW to record ADCP data. The RTK GPS setup used Topcon HiPer V antennas with an FC-6000 controller and a Seafloor Hydrolite-TM sonar depth sounder for the bathymetry survey. Tidal currents were measured using a Teledyne RDI RiverRay ADCP, which was side-mounted over the port gunwale of the vessel (Fig. 2(b)). The ADCP measured vertical profiles of water speed/direction and its own speed over the ground, measuring absolute current velocity. The software controlled the ADCP and integrated the GPS positions to geolocate every ADCP profile measurement, recording all the device outputs in a series of data files to the PC hard drive.

Fig. 2. (a) Vessel-mounted equipment and offsets; (b) ADCP and RTK GPS receiver mounted on the vessel.

2.2. Bathymetry

An RTK GPS and integrated depth sounder were used for the bathymetric survey along pre-planned transects. The full extent of available bathymetric survey data is presented in Fig. 3(a). The survey team encountered thick kelp beds extending approximately 150ft from shore, preventing the bathymetry survey from covering the entire width of the Inlet. Importantly, there was a significant level of turbulence in the area north and west of Village Rock (Fig.1(b)), where the survey team collected velocity data throughout the tidal cycle. Fig. 3(b) shows the filtered bathymetry data (exploratory 3D mesh plot).

Fig. 3. (a) All-inclusive bathymetric and GPS survey points; (b) Visualization of filtered bathymetric data (exploratory mesh plot).

2.3. Velocity variation

A series of four transect lines were studied throughout the flood portion of a tidal cycle on September 28-29, 2022 (Fig. 4(a)). An overlay plot of survey transect lines over the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) bathymetric chart [10] is shown in Fig. 4(b). Quasi-synoptic current speed and direction measurements were recorded throughout the 11 survey cycles. The strongest flows were observed during the flood phase of the tide with peak speeds of $1.35m/s - 2.4m/s$. The strongest flows were found consistently along lines #2 and #3, close to the Village Rock, in an area of relatively shallow water depth. Fig. 5(a) shows a graphical representation of the quasi-synoptic map of the flow vectors. The cross-section of the transect is graphically represented by the color-contoured plot (Fig. 5(b)). The horizontal axes represent the distance from the shoreline, and the vertical axes represent the water depth, both in meters. Color represents the speed of the water. Dark blue indicates a weak flow, and orange/red indicates a high-speed flow. The perspective of each contour plot is from the south looking upstream.

Fig. 4. (a) Approximate location of transects for velocity measurements; (b) Measured bathymetry (with a NOAA bathymetry chart underlay), along with the four transect lines in the lower inlet (close to the Village Rock) for velocity monitoring.

Fig. 5. (a) Velocity vector map for survey cycle #9; (b) Velocity contour for survey cycle #9 (Transect Line #2).

3. Hydrodynamic modeling

The measured velocity described above did not cover the spatial extent of Kootznahoo Inlet. With bathymetric data, the team could approximate the Inlet's cross-sectional area at various locations. The NW portion of the Inlet was not studied, as the cross-sectional area was determined to be much greater than at the SE portion; measurements were only carried out at the four indicated transects (Fig. 4(a) and Fig. 4(b)). Also, the velocity data was collected over a limited time and only on the flood tide. To have a velocity estimate that extended over the full extent of the study domain and for the full extent of the tidal cycle, a one-dimensional hydrodynamic model (DYNLET) was developed for the study site [11]. DYNLET is a numerical model used to determine tidal velocity and water level fluctuations in estuaries and inlets. It uses an implicit finite-difference scheme to solve the full one-dimensional shallow water equations (Equations (1) and (2)).

$$\frac{\partial Q}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\frac{Q^2}{A} \right) = -gAS_f + gB\tau_s - gAS_e - gA \left(\frac{\partial z}{\partial y} \right) \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial Q}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial A}{\partial t} - q = 0 \quad (2)$$

where Q is the flow rate, t is the time, y is the horizontal distance along a channel, A is the cross-sectional area, g is the acceleration due to gravity, S_f is the friction slope, B is the width of the top of the channel cross-section, τ_s is the surface shear stress due to wind, S_e is the transition loss rate with distance, Z is the water surface elevation, and q is the lateral inflow or outflow per unit channel length per unit time.

The principal inputs to the DYNLET model include the model spatial extent, bathymetry, and boundary condition data. The model spatial extent was represented by three channels, with channel 1 coincident with the quadrilateral shown in Fig. 1(b) and two additional channels connected to and landward of channel 1 (Fig. 6(a)). The three channels were connected at a single junction which was located at the southeast end of channel 1 (Fig. 1(b), Fig. 6(a)). The hydrographic survey described above allowed us to define channel 1 in detail. The spatial extent and bathymetry of channels 2 and 3 were estimated based on an analysis of Google Earth imagery and using NOAA navigation charts. Boundary condition data were comprised of three elements, including water surface elevation (relative to MSL) at the ocean boundary of channel 1 (i.e., the NW extent of the study site shown in Fig. 1(b)). The second and third elements of the boundary condition data were the volumetric flow rates at the landward end of channels 2 and 3, which were set to zero. The DYNLET hydrodynamic model was calibrated by comparing observed and modeled velocity in the Inlet (Fig. 6(b)) and adjusting the spatial extent of channels 2 and 3 until there was good agreement between observed and modeled velocity. Fig. 6(a) shows the spatial distribution of velocity on the flood tide at 1:00 am on September 29, 2022; Fig. 6(b) shows the temporal distribution of velocity along the thalweg of the 4 velocity transects (Fig. 4(a)). Tidal flow in Kootznahoo Inlet reflects the presence of both the

incident and reflected tidal wave and exhibits tidal co-oscillation [12]. With tidal co-oscillation, the water surface elevation and the tidal velocity are out of phase (Fig. 6(b)). The magnitude of the flood and ebb velocities in the Inlet reflect the tidal prism which is the volume of water that passes through the inlet each tidal cycle.

Fig. 6. (a) Contour plot of the spatial distribution of velocity on the flood tide at 1:00 AM 9/29/22; (b) Modeled thalweg velocity as a function of time along Transects 1-4, with velocity observations on Transect 2.

4. Conclusion

The characterization and hydrodynamic modeling of the Kootznahoo Inlet uncovered several interesting features of the study site. Currents in the Kootznahoo Inlet result from tidal co-oscillation. Bathymetric analysis showed that the depth and the cross-sectional area decreased significantly from the north of the inlet towards the Village Rock, resulting in a stronger current close to the Village Rock (as is evident from the velocity vector plots). The strongest tidal currents observed during the survey were found near the SE side of the Village Rock, in 20-m deep water. The highest current speeds observed during the survey were approximately 2.3 m/s and found along Transect 2. The average of the measured current velocities was around 1.7 m/s. Calibration of the DYNLET hydrodynamic model using observed water velocity from Transect 2 enabled an estimate of tidal velocity throughout the Inlet. In agreement with the velocity measurements, the DYNLET hydrodynamic model indicated that the highest velocities would be close to the SE side of the Inlet, proximate to Village Rock.

Acknowledgments

The information, data, or work presented herein was partly funded by the Advanced Research Projects Agency-Energy (ARPA-E), U.S. Department of Energy (DoE), under Award Number DE-AR0001447. The views and opinions of authors expressed herein do not necessarily state or reflect those of the United States Government or any agency thereof. The authors thank Michael Baker International for conducting the bathymetry and ADCP studies at the Kootznahoo Inlet. Thanks, are also due to Jon Wood (Ocean Data Technologies, Inc. (Hyannis, MA)) for providing the base scripts for the raw ADCP data processing.

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